

2020 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC

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Author(s)	C. Pascoe	
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2021-02-11	0.1	Initial Report for DDC managers. This includes the separate SEDAC statistics but does not yet include browser statistics or the country by country breakdown.
2021-02-12	1.0	Completed outstanding sections

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1. Summary

This report provides details of how the DDC web site, ipcc-data.org, was used in the 12 months from January 1st 2020 to December 31st 2020. The information presented here is generated using the Google Analytics service; providing a range of different statistics that cover both temporal and spatial trends. Only non-bounce sessions in which users have interacted with the website have been used in this analysis.

The annual DDC page views for 2020 show a 21% decrease in usage compared to 2019 but are nevertheless comparable to the number page views received in previous years. 2020 began with page views at the upper end of the range and ended at the lower end of the range. The annual total for 2020 is above that seen in 2017 and 2018.

The Home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC. In 2020 Europe was the most active region using DDC resources.

2. Evolution of User Sessions

The number of DDC page views recorded in 2020 are about 21% less than those received in 2019. The decrease in usage began in mid-March 2020 and the negative trend (relative to previous years) continued until August 2020 whereupon the pattern of use began to show a similar behaviour to previous years albeit from a lower baseline.

Figure 1: Time series of weekly DDC page views for non-bounce sessions. The time axis is shown in weeks from January 1st. The thick black line shows the page views in the period from January 1st to December 31st 2020, thin grey lines show the page views in previous years (2017, 2018 and 2019).

Figure 2: Annual page views for non-bounce sessions from 2017 – 2020.

3. Access Patterns by Page on the DDC

This page view analysis examines the 50 most visited URLs on the IPCC-DDC.

The IPCC-DDC home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC, receiving 15% of page views in 2020 (Figure 3). Other popular pages are those that explain some of the basic science behind climate change such as: Understanding the observational record; Projected emissions and concentrations of carbon dioxide. It is clear that users are interested in using the DDC to access data and information about the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5).

Figure 4 shows the number of unique page views and number of entrances for the most used pages on the DDC during 2020. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

Most users arriving at the DDC continue to do so via the Home page. It is reassuring to know that the first DDC page users generally see is our home page because this is where we provide information about the purpose of the site and an overview of the content that we provide. Information pages about the scenario process for AR5 and the description of RCPs are also places of entry to the DDC. 2020 showed that users are also arriving at the DDC via the Glossary.

Most users visiting the guidance pages navigate there from another page on the DDC, this fits with the behaviour of a person who, having found some interesting data, decides to use our guidance documents to learn how to use it.

The pageview statistics for pages hosted by the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Centre (SEDAC) is shown in Table 2 and Figure 5.

Distribution of page views across the DDC

Figure 3: Distribution of page views for the most visited pages on the IPCC-DDC during 2020.

Page on the DDC	URL	Number of Views	%
Home	www.ipcc-data.org/index.html	28,159	14.3
Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/index.html	14,336	7.3
CO2	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html	10,430	5.3
Simulations	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/index.html	9,057	4.6
Climate Model Output	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/index.html	5,839	3.0
AR5 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	5,272	2.7
Glossary - R	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/glossary/glossary_r.html	5,263	2.7
Regional Scatter Plots	www.ipcc-data.org/syn/tar_scatter/index.html	4,949	2.5
What is a GCM?	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html	4,650	2.4
AR4 Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/ar4_global.html	4,610	2.3
Climate Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_envdata.html	4,577	2.3
Guidance	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html	4,158	2.1
Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5°C	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/SR15/index.html	3,780	1.9
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	3,766	1.9
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	3,526	1.8

Table 1: Distribution of page views for the most visited pages on the IPCC-DDC during 2020. This table contains the same information as the pie chart in figure 3 but with the page URLs shown.

Figure 4: The number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) during 2020. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views. Note that the “unique page views” statistic lists all pages that are visited in a session, it does not take into account the number of times a page is visited during that session.

SEDAC Page	SEDAC Page on the DDC	Page views	Unique Page views	Entrances
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	3,766	2,089	1,292
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	3,526	2,256	1,468
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed_ar5/index.html	2,839	1,972	1,008
SRES Emissions Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/index.html	2,371	1,297	796
Socio-Economic Baseline Dataset	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/baseline/index.html	1,980	1,251	643
Socio-Economic Data and Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/index.html	1,500	879	722
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed_ar5/ar5_2.html	1,472	817	20
Scenario Process for AR5: The IPCC and Scenario Development	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/ipcc_scenarios.html	1,067	792	95
Scenario Process for AR5: Parallel Phase: Climate Modeling Activities	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/parallel_climate_modeling.html	931	709	27
IPCC IS92 Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/is92/index.html	911	568	235
IPCC AR4 Observed Climate Change Impacts	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed/index.html	897	694	120
Scenario Process for AR5: Parallel Phase: New Narratives and Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/parallel_nat_scen.html	761	512	60
Scenario Process for AR5: Scenarios Background Information	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/scenario_background.html	517	396	34
Scenario Process for AR5: Scenario Process Overview	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/scenario_overview.html	454	355	29
Scenario Process for AR5: References and Resources	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/reference_resource.html	308	226	28

Table 2: Distribution of page views for the 15 most visited DDC pages hosted by the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Centre (SEDAC).

Figure 5: The number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) for the SEDAC hosted pages of the DDC.

4. Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC

In 2020 Europe was the most active region using DDC resources (Figure 6). Overall there was a 21.7% fall in the number of DDC sessions from 2019 to 2020 however the fall was experienced differently in different continents (Figure 7). The smallest fall in sessions was seen in Central and Southern Americas where the fall was just 10.8%, the largest fall in sessions was seen in North America where the fall was 28.2%.

Figure 8 names the top 17 countries that make use of the DDC. Users in 7 countries account for 52% of all sessions: USA 18%, UK 8%, India 6%, China 6%, Germany 5%, Canada 5%, France 4%. “other” countries not listed in Figure 8 account for 29% of user sessions. A full breakdown by country of the DDC user sessions in 2019 and 2020 is shown in appendix A.

Figure 6: The geographical distribution of IPCC-DDC sessions by continent for 2020.

Figure 7: The percentage change in session numbers from 2019 to 2020 by continent.

Figure 8: The geographical distribution of IPCC-DDC user sessions by country for 2020.

Sessions initiated by users in Europe, Asia and North America account for 85% of DDC activity (Figure 7) however approximately half of the DDC sessions are initiated by users in just seven countries (Figure 8).

5. Browser Statistics

The IPCC-DDC site is available and accessible to all the major internet browsers and operating systems. English is the most used language setting, accounting for 60% of sessions (Figure 9). Chrome is the most popular browser, accounting for 71% of sessions and Windows is the most popular operating system, accounting for 74% of sessions (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Language settings for DDC user sessions during 2020.

Figure 10: Browser and technology characteristics of DDC user sessions with information about Browsers, Operating Systems that are used to access the DDC during 2019.

Appendix

A full breakdown, by country, of the DDC user sessions during 2020 and also during 2019 for comparison.

Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions	Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions
United States	7013	9948	Argentina	242	262
United Kingdom	3360	4495	South Africa	242	311
China	2498	3570	Pakistan	236	290
India	2292	3114	Philippines	218	278
Germany	1990	2669	Peru	202	205
Canada	1858	2412	New Zealand	195	296
France	1477	1761	Ireland	188	226
Italy	1320	1418	Poland	187	234
Australia	1272	1488	Finland	181	374
Brazil	1029	1200	Ecuador	175	144
Spain	961	1346	Vietnam	150	171
Netherlands	885	1185	Bangladesh	138	171
Japan	824	1199	Morocco	128	94
Iran	688	957	(not set)	128	119
Sweden	560	852	Nigeria	123	161
South Korea	552	576	Israel	111	78
Mexico	482	545	Egypt	110	108
Belgium	464	569	United Arab Emirates	105	57
Switzerland	453	659	Hungary	103	113
Indonesia	440	482	Nepal	103	107
Turkey	394	357	Kenya	101	143
Taiwan	384	425	Czechia	98	153
Hong Kong	363	314	Nicaragua	89	15
Denmark	352	434	Sri Lanka	88	70
Colombia	346	384	Bolivia	81	48
Portugal	325	343	Romania	81	82
Greece	299	275	Ukraine	67	74
Malaysia	292	291	Uganda	60	56
Russia	288	245	Ghana	59	57
Chile	282	393	Costa Rica	57	66
Thailand	276	283	Algeria	57	53
Singapore	272	250	Luxembourg	57	60
Norway	269	359	Iraq	54	53
Ethiopia	262	382	Saudi Arabia	52	58
Austria	257	342	Tanzania	49	92

Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions	Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions
Lithuania	48	37	Kuwait	18	7
Slovakia	48	40	Latvia	18	26
Cambodia	44	56	Cuba	17	6
Jordan	41	54	Myanmar (Burma)	17	43
Tunisia	39	46	Namibia	17	10
Serbia	38	25	Guyana	16	11
Slovenia	38	37	Georgia	15	15
Zimbabwe	36	48	Malta	15	13
Burkina Faso	34	17	Mauritius	15	14
Croatia	34	38	Belarus	14	15
Bulgaria	33	41	Cyprus	14	32
Côte d'Ivoire	33	59	Afghanistan	13	8
Cameroon	33	32	Mali	13	4
Trinidad & Tobago	33	44	Malawi	13	8
Benin	32	18	Azerbaijan	12	8
Panama	31	24	Laos	12	23
Venezuela	30	14	Syria	12	26
Madagascar	29	33	Senegal	11	40
Kazakhstan	28	14	Bosnia & Herzegovina	10	14
Lebanon	28	28	Paraguay	10	33
Zambia	28	19	Yemen	10	3
Guatemala	27	43	Botswana	9	12
Sudan	27	34	Honduras	9	15
Uruguay	27	19	Togo	9	16
Estonia	25	38	Bahrain	8	7
Fiji	25	16	Dominican Republic	8	103
Mozambique	24	58	Moldova	8	7
Bhutan	23	6	Uzbekistan	8	11
Brunei	22	36	Monaco	7	3
Jamaica	22	16	Sierra Leone	7	4
Oman	22	11	Libya	6	4
Iceland	21	33	Macao	6	8
Qatar	21	17	Niger	6	19
Mongolia	20	11	Kyrgyzstan	5	6
El Salvador	19	9	Lesotho	5	11

Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions	Country	2020 Sessions	2019 Sessions
North Macedonia	5	9	Guinea	2	1
Palestine	5	10	Guadeloupe	2	2
Rwanda	5	24	Jersey	2	1
Tajikistan	5		Chad	2	2
Albania	4	6	Antigua & Barbuda	1	8
Armenia	4	3	Aruba	1	
Cook Islands	4	1	Curaçao	1	2
Guinea-Bissau	4	1	Djibouti	1	7
St. Lucia	4		Dominica	1	
Montenegro	4	3	Micronesia	1	1
Réunion	4	9	Gabon	1	1
Suriname	4	4	Greenland	1	
Turkmenistan	4		Guam	1	
Kosovo	4	13	Liberia	1	2
Barbados	3	7	St. Martin	1	
Bahamas	3	1	Marshall Islands	1	
Belize	3	5	Mauritania	1	1
Congo - Kinshasa	3	12	Maldives	1	2
Central African Republic	3		Papua New Guinea	1	8
Congo - Brazzaville	3		Svalbard & Jan Mayen	1	
Faroe Islands	3	7	Eswatini	1	4
Grenada	3	3	British Virgin Islands	1	1
Gambia	3	2	U.S. Virgin Islands	1	1
Haiti	3	4	Vanuatu		1
Comoros	3	5	Burundi		1
Liechtenstein	3	6	Anguilla		1
Puerto Rico	3	19			
Seychelles	3	1			
Somalia	3	3			
Sint Maarten	3				
Timor-Leste	3	2			
Andorra	2	1			
Angola	2	2			
Bermuda	2	2			
Gibraltar	2	2	Total	40,996	52,286

